
DEATH ON THE OPERATING TABLE: NIGHTMARE OF THE ANAESTHETIST. SEVEN YEARS
REVIEW IN A NIGERIAN GENERAL HOSPITAL.

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ABSTRACT

Death on the operating table (DOT) is a phenomenon that is unpalatable to the anaesthetist: one which occurs at one time or the other in his career. These are patients who suffered cardiac arrests on the operating table whose resuscitation failed. DOT is fast becoming uncommon with the sophistication of medical equipments and improved standards of care. A 7-year review of deaths on the operating table at a general hospital in Warri was done. Of the 1187 patients operated in theatre 10 of these died on the operating table. Four of the DOTs showed poor prognostic indices in the preoperative period as assessed by their American society of Anesthesiology (ASA) physical status 4 or 5. 60% of the DOTs were pregnancy related. Apart from the morbidity of these patients, the category of anaesthetist was contributory. This also played a role in the outcome in the paediatric DOT. Outcome in some of these patients would have been better had they been handled by the more senior and experienced anaesthetists or by junior residents under direct supervision of their consultants. Faulty machines and inadequate monitoring are potential causes of mortality as demonstrated in the patient for tonsillectomy with obstructive sleep apnea who was anaesthetised by the consultant. The current use of simulators in the training of anaesthetists have been useful in developing skills that may be called upon in times of stress especially among junior and less experienced anaesthetists.

KEYWORDS: operating table, paediatric, consultants, anaesthetists, general hospital, Warri

INTRODUCTION

Anaesthetic death is classified as death within 24-48 h of administering anaesthesia to a patient. Sometimes however the primary cause of death may be the pathology which brought the patient to surgery. Anaesthesia is sometimes known to affect outcome which is what makes it mandatory to prognosticate using risk assessment scores like the Goldman risk and American society of Anesthesiology (ASA) indices. Factors that cause death on the operating table include poor patient preparation, choice of anaesthetic at induction, and performance of anaesthetist. Poor cardiovascular and ventilatory monitoring are other important causes of death (Arbous et al 2001). Administering the safest kind of anaesthetic is crucial to getting a good outcome. When a seemingly well patient dies on the operating table even in unanticipated cases, the standard and quality of care can be questioned. Literatures on cardiac arrest are common compared to events of death on the operating table which is being x-rayed in this retrospective study.

METHOD

A 7-year review of death on the operating table from 2003-2010 was done in a general Hospital in Delta state, Nigeria. Operating theatre records of patients who died in theatre were reviewed along with available anaesthetic records after ethical approval.

Their surgeries were categorized into elective and emergencies. They were also categorized into their different surgical specialties. The patients' bio-data and reasons for surgery were identified along with their American Society of Anaesthetists (ASA) risk status. The level of anaesthetic personnel that anaesthetised the patients was also noted. The anaesthetic staffs were two anaesthetic nurses, two anaesthetic medical officers and two consultant staff in a busy centre that can sometimes be overwhelming. The anaesthetic staffs take regular routine lists and calls. Death on the table was identified as patients who had anaesthesia administered in the operating room and certified dead after unsuccessful cardiopulmonary resuscitation. The absence of a functional anaesthesia recovery room made recovery of patients on the operating table a regular routine. Patients who were successfully resuscitated after cardiac arrest were excluded from the study.

RESULTS

Of the 1187 patients operated on there were 10 deaths (table 1 & 2). One death was recorded in patients for local anaesthesia while 8 were from general anaesthesia and one from regional anaesthesia. The patient who died at local infiltration showed features of intravascular injection of local anaesthetic and toxicity. The anaesthetic was administered by the surgeon. Six patients died during emergency caesarean section (60%). Five had general anaesthesia and one had spinal anaesthesia (figure 1). Obstetric DOT which constituted the highest in incidence may be reflective of the high caesarean section compared to other surgeries. Of this number four had pregnancy induced hypertension, one prolonged labour and one died from ante partum haemorrhage and was exsanguinated on the table from non-availability of blood to match rapid losses despite administration of colloids and crystalloids (figure 2). Two children died at elective tonsillectomy; one from difficult intubation and the other as result of obstructive sleep apnea, hypoxia and subsequent cardiac arrest from which he did not recover.

DISCUSSION

When patients die on the operating table it may be disease related, patient related, surgery or surgeon related, anaesthesia related or even anaesthetist related. In this study we reviewed the incidence of intraoperative deaths in the operative room in a secondary care facility in Delta state Nigeria over a 7-year period. Of the 1187 patients operated on, ten died on the operating table. This constituted 0.1% (118 per 10,000). This figure is high and staggering when compared with the study by Olsson and Hallen (1988) that was 2.4 per 10,000. In a review by Braz et al (2009) comparing literature data from different parts of the world between 1954 and 1989 and figures from 1990 to 2006, anaesthesia related deaths decreased from 0.30-7.91 per 10,000 to 0.10 to 5.91. Perioperative mortality declined from 2.4 - 188.9 per 10,000 to 1.4-28.2 in the same periods being compared. In the study by Kubota et al (1994), the results of 30 years' experience did not support the hypothesis that all anesthetic CAs and deaths are preventable. However, careful clinical management can reduce their frequency to a lower level. Factors that cause anaesthesia-related death on the operating table include poor patient preparation, choice of anaesthetic at induction, and performance of anaesthetist. Poor cardiovascular and ventilatory monitoring are other important causes of death (Arbous *et al.*, 2001). The study by Keenan and Boyan (1991) support the hypothesis that improved respiratory monitoring was effective in decreasing anesthetic morbidity. The rate for preventable arrests due to respiratory causes declined significantly and accounted for most of the observed decrease in the overall anesthetic cardiac arrest rate. The rates for preventable nonrespiratory arrests and nonpreventable arrests did not change significantly.

Of the mortalities reviewed in our centre, obstetric patients were 60% which may be reflective of the high turnover of obstetric surgeries in the institution compared to other surgeries. Other studies indicate a three-fold higher risk of pediatric patients than in adults; they also suggest that emergency patients were six times at risk than elective cases (Fleisher 2005). All the caesarean patients were done as emergencies most of whom were unbooked in the antenatal clinic. Causes of death in the obstetric patients were elevated uncontrolled blood pressure, inadequate ventilation compounded by over-sedation pre induction of anaesthesia and hypovolaemia. One patient died from hypotension secondary to high spinal anaesthesia. The status of the anaesthetist in this case was less than a physician. Other studies have shown that the experience of the anaesthetist is an important factor in anaesthesia related maternal mortality (Morgan 1987). Though maternal mortality has been noted to reduce with the increased use of regional techniques for caesarean sections, skill and experience and detailed application of knowledge is essential to ensure this seeming advantage over general anaesthesia (Braz *et al* 2006). Maternal mortality figures in Nigeria presently stand at 1100 to 1500 per 100,000 (Hogan *et al.*, 2010). In order to keep these figures to the barest minimum, it is important to enforce guidelines and standards in the care of the vulnerable group of persons. Nigeria has the second highest rate of maternal mortality in the world. At present, 1 in every 18 women dies giving birth versus 1 in 4,800 in the US. The issue of maternal mortality in Nigeria is a complex one affected by both medical and social factors that may require dealing with all factors simultaneously (Pitterson L 2010, Lanre-Abass 2008).

The 66 years old patient for herniorrhaphy who died after infiltration of local anaesthetic showed features of intravascular injection and toxicity. This was administered by the surgical registrar, without an anaesthetist in attendance. The elderly is at increased risk at surgery like children especially in the presence of co-morbidities: as current evidence shows that age alone can no longer be considered an independent risk factor for a poor outcome following general surgery (Lee *et al.*, 1999). Also intravascular injection of local anaesthetics is known to cause cardiac arrest (Lee 2006).

Deaths on the operating table in patients classified as ASA 1 or 2 can be quite devastating to the anaesthetist especially in seemingly healthy children. Two children in this review died while undergoing tonsillectomy. They had no obvious co morbid diseases. The cause of death in the first instance was difficult airway while in the second case a child's condition of obstructive sleep apnea was worsened by a faulty anaesthetic machine delivering hypoxic gas mixtures and non-availability of pulse oximetry. These cases go on to prove that with increase in sophistication of monitoring devices and equipment, the safety profile of our patients can be enhanced, Minimum monitoring devices should be available before procedures are embarked on. When the Harvard minimum safety guidelines are adopted and practiced, unnecessary morbidity and mortality can be avoided (ASA 1998).

Availability of blood and blood products posed a challenge in the patient with placenta accrete. In that patient the blood available was simply insufficient to resuscitate the patient, as the anaesthetist helplessly watched the patient bleed to death on the operating table despite the administration of crystalloids and plasma expanders. Blood donation is increasingly becoming a challenge as people perceive blood transfusion to be risky: and are afraid of testing positive for human immunodeficiency virus (HIV). Also an increasing number of donors test positive for HIV and hepatitis. This has put a limit on blood available for transfusion (Olaiya *et al.*, 2004). With this background, it is tragic that currently 25% of maternal deaths are attributed to non-availability of blood for transfusion (Kumari 2001). Occasionally, request for blood from the National transfusion service proved futile from non-availability, mainly from the fast depletion of their stock from non-availability of voluntary donors; a situation which may be addressed by support from collaborating agencies like the Red cross and World Health Organisation (WHO).

For decades' efforts have been made to improve safety of patients during surgery and anaesthesia standards and guidelines set up by different bodies. There is growing interest in the use of simulators to test and train individuals and their ability to react to simulated stress (Holzmam 1995). All these efforts seem to be having a positive impact evidenced by an increasing safety profile of anaesthetic and surgical practice worldwide.

CONCLUSION

Death on the operating is a phenomenon the anaesthetist may have to face in a lifetime of practice, which none the less is becoming rare. In undeveloped nations like ours it is not as rare an occurrence especially in the absence of improved and modern facilities for intraoperative patient monitoring. The pre morbid state of patients among many other factors contributes to this unfortunate event. Improved anaesthetic services and standard intraoperative monitoring can limit this trend in our environment.

Abbreviations

DOT- Death on the operating table
ASA- American Society of Anesthesiologists
HIV-Human immunodeficiency virus
WHO- World Health Organisation
GA- General Anaesthesia
LA- Local Anaesthesia

Competing interests

The author states that there are no competing interests

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Table 1

Obstetric DOT		TYPE OF ANAESTHESIA
6		
PIH	4	3GA+1REGIONAL
OBST labour	1	GA
Antepartum haemorrhage	1	GA
General Surgical DOT		
2		
Herniorrhaphy	1	Local anaesthesia
Exploratory laparotomy	1	GA
Paediatric DOT		
2		
Difficult intubation	1	GA
Post obstructive sleep apnea	1	GA

Figure 1: PATTERN OF DEATHS ON THE OPERATING TABLE (DOT)

Figure 2: OBSTETRIC DOT

Table 2:

S/N	AGE	ASA Status	sexx	DIAGNOSIS	TYPE OF SURGERY	TYPE OF ANAESTHESIA	LEVEL OF ANAESTHETIC
1	24yrss	1E	F	Obstructed Labour	Emergency caesarean section	GA	Registrar
2	33yrs	4	F	Eclampsia	Emergency Caesarean section	GA	Registrar
3	66yrs	1	M	Inguino-scrotal hernia	Hemiorrhaphy (Elective)	LA	Registrar
4	25yrs	2E	F	Pregnancy induced hypertension	Emergency Caesarean section	GA	Registrar
5	2yrs	1	M	Adenotonsillitis	Adenotonsillectomy (Elective)	GA	Registrar/Anaesthetic Nurse
6	25yrs	4E	F	Placenta previa Placenta accreta	Emergency Caesarean section	GA	Consultant
7	28yrs	5	F	Huge fibroid in 32 weeks gestation+PIH	Elective Caesarean section	GA	Consultant
8	2yrs	1	M	Adenotonsillitis Obstructive sleep apnea	Adenotonsillectomy (Elective)	GA	Consultant
9	30yrs	2-3	F	Pregnancy induced hypertension/Obesity	Emergency caesarean section	Spinal Anaesthesia	Anaesthetic Nurse
10	50yrs	4	F	Intrabdominal tumour with lung metastasis	Exploratory Laparotomy (Elective)	GA	Consultant